

Quantum Geometry of an Electron: the Golden Number and Internal Half-Oscillator

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Internal properties of an electron at rest are studied, applying a model based on the concept of the particle being nonlinear form of electromagnetic wave (Williamson 1997) and on geometric interpretation of Dirac's equation (Hestenes 1990), with an additional assumption that the positive and negative solutions of it are correlated with different energy states of the wave packet, switching at the Zitterbewegung frequency (Sasabe and Tsuchiya 2008). Calculations of the quantum radius of an electron in these states are performed, yielding surprising results, linked together by the golden number in third power. The particle's rest mass is described as a sum of energy resulting from the wavelength assigned to the quantum radius and negative internal potential energy binding the wave packet, probably via a self-interaction involving the strong force. Applying this hypothesis enables easy calculation of the anomalous magnetic moment of an electron with accuracy at the level of 10^{-12} . Transformations of the particle's rest energy are shown as a kind of half-oscillator, belonging to the ground state and correlated with fermion properties (return of the spinor to the starting conditions after a rotation by 720°). A modification of the procedure of Dirac's equation normalization based on this approach is proposed to solve the negative energy problem. The solution can be valid even if the reconstructed physical model of an electron is considered not proven enough; in such a case it should be treated as a quantum geometry model of the particle's pilot wave.

electron quantum geometry, Dirac's equation, negative-energy problem, golden number, electric dipole moment, anomalous magnetic moment, strong force

1. Introduction

Quantum equivalent of an electron's geometry is an important aspect of the knowledge representation in quantum mechanics [1], worth to be studied although at the current stage of scientific development it is still impossible to clearly state whether it encodes some kind of information about the real geometry of this particle or is just a property of the formal language. Nevertheless, such efforts can digest and deepen the knowledge of the quantum mechanics foundations and provide clues for their further development. This type of research contributes, as well, to the broader debate on the possible connections between quantum mechanics and classical physics in real space, undertaken, for example, in the following recently published works: [2-5].

A review of scientific literature shows also that there exists a rich set of other data, including empirical ones, which considered parallel with the image of electron's quantum geometry enable formulating well-motivated hypothesis on this particle's physical nature and geometry, suggesting indirectly an existence of some analogies between these two geometrical orders. If they are even partially confirmed in the future, it will lead to a

significant shifting the boundaries of knowledge, initiating the study of the structure of matter at the next, deeper and more fundamental level. If no, they can be regardless an inspiration for new discoveries and ideas, because in most cases the new approach arise from testing hypotheses and, especially, associating various facts to obtain a consistent picture of the object or process studied, not from performing standard procedures. Last but not least, the results of such research can have a didactic value, providing intuitive tools for learning and teaching quantum mechanics, in a similar way like the Bohr's model of an atom, recognized finally as unphysical, is applied up to now in schools, because it facilitates learning fundamental chemistry.

Due to all these reasons, that difficult but fascinating problem is selected as a topic for this heuristic study, aimed at an electron's quantum geometry reconstruction via a discussion of the previous theoretical models together with a comprehensive meta-analysis of experimental and calculated data related to the physics of this particle. The further and more ambitious goal is to apply this model as a tool which enables to find and describe some undiscovered internal properties of an electron at rest.

2. Methodological and conceptual foundations

The starting point for the analysis was the work [1] published by David Hestenes, who using space-time algebra proved that geometry is encoded in Dirac's theory of an electron. The imaginary unit present in the equations acts as a generator of rotation of some point, moving at linear velocity equal to the speed of light in vacuum (c) along a helix; the radius of the circle drawn by this point is $\hbar/(2m_e c)$ (i.e. $1.93079634 \times 10^{-13}$ m; the parameter \hbar is reduced Planck's constant, m_e is the rest mass of an electron), and the angular velocity ($1.552688139 \times 10^{21}$ rad s^{-1}) with the resulting rotation frequency by 360° ($2.471179928 \times 10^{20}$ s^{-1}) are identical to the so-called Zitterbewegung effect (ZBW) [1].

It is convenient to interpret this moving point as a point-like front of electromagnetic wave. The concept of an electron as yet unrecognized form of electromagnetic wave with nonlinear propagation geometry has been known long, referred to in quite numerous publications [for example, 6-10], and although it is accepted still only by a part of the scientific community, it is well motivated.

The electromagnetic nature of a quantum mechanical electron is indicated, among others, by the speed of light at which the point described by the Hestenes' model moves, because, as it is well-known, photons are the only observed objects that can reach it, due to the lack of rest mass. In such a system the mass would be an external feature of the whole wave packet, not of the front. Another significant property is the wave nature of an electron [11] manifesting as an ability to diffraction, as well as electric and magnetic field production [12]. The particles' image as a non-linear form of electromagnetic wave fits also well with the mechanism of matter creation. This process emerges as a result of collision of high-energy (at least ~ 0.511 MeV) photons and is reversible (the contact of an electron with its antiparticle, i.e. a positron, causes their decay into photons) [13]. It suggests rather yet unknown "phase transition" of the photons, consisting in changing a form, than transformation into something

fundamentally different, especially that under conditions of extremely strong electric or magnetic field, close to the value given by the so-called Schwinger limit (i.e. conditions typical for the process of particle creation), electromagnetic wave is bent [14]. It is worth noting that under certain conditions, even photons with lower energy can behave similarly to electrons [15] and electrons to photons [16], which is a fingerprint of their common nature, too. In addition, in the literature there are hypothesized that electrons, photons, and other elementary particles may have a common source in a string network condensation in vacuum [17]. Such kinship justifies the search for mathematical relationships between them, as well as thinking of an electron as the form (or state) of a photon, and vice versa. It is also in line with the well-known postulate of Darwin, who stated that since matter and light show the same wave-particle duality, then a similar formalism should be used to describe them [18].

A study of the current version of this formalism reveals that there are characteristic mathematical relationships supporting the above-mentioned concept of an electron as a form of nonlinear electromagnetic wave, or at least proving that this is its quantum-mechanical image. The radius of the circle (let it be assigned as $\langle R_e \rangle$) determined by Hestenes directly from the analysis of the Dirac's equation using space-time algebra [1] can be calculated alternatively on the basis of the energy balance of the electron creation process, treating the value of the z -component of the particle spin ($\hbar/2$) as an angular momentum of its electromagnetic wave front in the xy plane, i.e.:

$$p_f \times \langle R_e \rangle = \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad (1)$$

Since the energy of the photon (E_f) is equal to the product of its momentum (p_f) and the speed of light, it can be determined as follows:

$$E_f = p_f c = \frac{\hbar c}{2\langle R_e \rangle} \quad (2)$$

From the principle of energy conservation it is known that the energy of a photon forming an electron must be equal to the energy stored as the rest mass ($m_e c^2$) of the created particle:

$$\frac{\hbar c}{2\langle R_e \rangle} = m_e c^2 \quad (3)$$

Thus:

$$\langle R_e \rangle = \frac{\hbar}{2m_e c} \quad (4)$$

Similar semi-classical calculations of the quantum equivalent of an electron's radius, based on the value of its spin, have already been performed in various versions, e.g. using energy without use of the expression representing momentum [7] or with the classical formula for momentum, assuming that it is the mass of an electron multiplied by the velocity of light [19]. The version presented above aims to show an explicit relationship between the momentum of the parent photon and the quantum radius of the created electron. By the way, equation (1) is formally correlated with the Heisenberg uncertainty principle for an electron in 2D system (i.e. $\Delta P \Delta R \geq \hbar/2$, where $\Delta P \Delta R$ is the product of momentum and position uncertainty).

Therefore, the momentum of a rest electron's internal wave front together with the radius of this front's circular trajectory determines that limit of a measurement accuracy. This fact reveals that in the quantum mechanical description a position of an electron is identified with the position of its wave front, not of the whole wave packet, so from this point of view the particle appears as a point-like object (in the real space it may have a femtometer-scale size determined via high-energy scattering experiments [20] in contradiction to the results of Compton length measurements, referring to the entire structure).

However, this is still not all. As noted in [7, 8], the quantum dimension of an electron wave packet corresponds to exactly half of the wavelength ($1/2 \lambda_0$) of the parent photon with an energy of ~ 0.511 MeV. This is easy to show by comparing the circumference of the circle (let assign it as $\langle O_e \rangle$) from the Hestenes' model [1], with the value of $1/2 \lambda_0$ calculated on the basis of experimental values of Planck's constant (h), the speed of light in vacuum and the energy (E) corresponding to the rest mass of an electron (these values were taken from [21]):

$$\begin{aligned} \langle O_e \rangle &= 2\pi \langle R_e \rangle = 2 \times 3.14159265 \times 1.93079634 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m} = & (5) \\ &= 12.13155119 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \lambda_0 = \frac{hc}{2E} = \frac{4.135667696 \times 10^{-15} \text{ eVs} \times 299792458 \text{ ms}^{-1}}{2 \times 0.51099895069 \times 10^6 \text{ eV}} = 12.13155118 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m} \quad (6)$$

The difference of the last digit after the decimal point in the results of equations (5) and (6) is related only to the inaccuracy of the substituted numerical parameters, which is proven by the fact that the equality $\langle O_e \rangle = 1/2 \lambda_0$ can be derived alternatively from the general formulas (it is shown in the Supplementary Information (SI), section 1.). Thus, a single orbit performed by the wave front being a quantum-mechanical image of an electron encompasses exactly the size of a single phase of the parent photon electrical component oscillation; the second, opposite phase, falls on the next rotation, *vide* Fig. 1a.

Fig. 1. (a) Diagram of an electromagnetic wave compared with diagrams illustrating analogous alternating phases of oscillation of a rest electron as a fermion particle with a dimension of $1/2 \lambda_0$ of the parent photon; (b) diagram of both phases of electron oscillation showing a shift of the magnetic component with respect to the electrical component. The drawings were plotted using the sinusoidal function ((a), left) and equations (7)-(9) derived from it ((a), right, and (b)) for the conventional parameters: $\langle R_e \rangle = 1, E_0' = 1$ and $B_0' = 1$; in the case of (a), right, $z_B = B_0' \sin(\theta/2)$.

This phase inheritance gives the model particle geometric properties of a fermion, i.e. it takes a 720° rotation to return it to its initial state [22, 23]. A similar flat and sine-based scheme of an electron's electrical component, but without paying attention to its relationship with the characteristics of fermions, was proposed in [8]. There was also performed an interesting discussion of some experimental evidences for such two-dimensional electric field distribution, for example, so-called helical Mott scattering, the value of the magnetic moment of an electron or the ability of this particle to join other electrons, forming groups [8]. It can be added, as well, that cyclical zeroing of the electric field at the phase change point could explain physical mechanism of a phenomenon known as quantum tunnelling. This process may be facilitated by momentary decreasing and stoppage of the coulombic repulsion force between the electron and the potential barrier. Then, when the next electric phase begins, the rapidly increasing repulsive force throws the particle to the other side of the barrier.

It should be noticed, that an electron built as illustrated in Fig. 1 functions as a standing wave when it is at rest and the front propagates along a circle instead of helical path, because despite this internal movement there is no movement of the field's maxima and minima in space. Only oscillations occurs. This can give an explanation why as a result of ZBW there is no radiation emission, possible only during translational motion of the particle, driven by external forces. In the latter situation an electron has two components of electric field perturbation: in the direction of the translational motion it is a traveling wave, while in the plane of ZBW it is a standing wave. During a particle's acceleration the travelling component is subject to inertial force acting in a plane perpendicular to ZBW which causes detachment of a part of the electric field giving rise to new photons while the wave front circulating in the rest particle does not experience this force. The lack of ZBW-driven emission may be also related to the fact that, similarly as in the model proposed in [2], the inertia centre of an electron (localized inside of the wave packet ring and being also the spin centre) remains at rest when the translational motion of the particle does not occur.

According to the nature of an electromagnetic wave, the magnetic component (\vec{B}) of an electron should oscillate perpendicular to the plane of the electric field (\vec{E}) oscillation, at least in the initial segments of the vectors, as noted for example in [10, 8, 19]. Using Ockham's razor principle, which requires the simplest approach selection, it can be assumed that the form of magnetic component of an electron preserves the sinusoidal course of oscillations illustrated in Fig. 1a, and not the shape of a torus often assumed by researchers [7, 8]. Although the toroidal form of the \vec{B} field is characteristic for macroscopic current loops, in their case the mechanism of generating this field involves complex processes occurring during the simultaneous translational motion of many electrons. The exact geometry of this motion is still unknown and may give an image of the resultant field not reflecting the shape of the magnetic component of individual particle at rest.

Moreover, this component must be phase shifted by 90° in time with respect to the electrical component of the parent photon, which in the geometry of an electron (the angles assigned to the circle encompassing $1/2 \lambda_0$) gives a shift of the maximum of both components by 180° , so that the extreme of each of them emerges at the zero point of the other, cf. Fig. 1b.

The presence of such a shift is evidenced by the fact that at the phase change point of the electrical component oscillation the particle is not annihilated as a result of simultaneous zeroing of the both fields intensities, which, as it is not difficult to imagine, could lead to the restoration of the original linear geometry of wave propagation over a further section. Such a phase shift of both fields as a factor stabilizing the particle (of a slightly different geometry) was postulated in [19], but without presenting experimental premises for this hypothesis, showing that so untypical \vec{E} and \vec{B} configuration is physically possible and motivated.

Firstly, it was observed that when the reflected laser light beam creates a standing wave, this wave experiences a 90° phase shift in time between both components [24] and the electron in the model under consideration also contains a standing wave, at the ZBW plane.

Secondly, the same shift occurs in photons emitted by a dipole antenna at an early stage of their propagation, so-called near-field, which is estimated to be a half of the photon wavelength size; only later does the synchronization of \vec{E} and \vec{B} phases emerges [25]. This could be interpreted in such a way that the photon emitted from the antenna initially reproduces the order of an electron that radiated it.

It is worthy to add that the electric and magnetic component of an electron are characterized by a certain degree of independence, experimentally proven by a phenomenon known as a spin-charge separation [26]. The same phenomenon can be treated as an indirect but clear fingerprint of these components existence and their wave nature instead of a homogeneous, statistical and disorderly cloud of charge, sometimes assumed as an electron's "substance", especially in the contemporary didactics.

The image of both phases of a rest electron in Fig. 1b is described in a three-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system using the equations of the electric and magnetic field distribution vectors (\vec{c}_{loc} , \vec{E}_{loc} , \vec{B}_{loc}) of a photon propagating in time t (from the conventionally assumed initial moment t_0) along a circle with radius $\langle R_e \rangle = \hbar/(2m_e c)$, where $\theta = (4\pi c/\lambda)(t-t_0)$ [rad], and E_0' , B_0' are the normalized field amplitudes, expressed in arbitrary spatial units:

$$\vec{c}_{loc}: \begin{cases} x_c = \langle R_e \rangle \cos \theta \\ y_c = \langle R_e \rangle \sin \theta \\ z_c = 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$\vec{E}_{loc}: \begin{cases} x_E = (\langle R_e \rangle - E_0' \sin \frac{\theta}{2}) \cos \theta \\ y_E = (\langle R_e \rangle - E_0' \sin \frac{\theta}{2}) \sin \theta \\ z_E = 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$\vec{B}_{loc}: \begin{cases} x_B = \langle R_e \rangle \cos \theta \\ y_B = \langle R_e \rangle \sin \theta \\ z_B = B_0' \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The normalization of the amplitude of the fields is carried out as follows:

$$E'_0 = E_0 \frac{R_u}{E_u} \quad (10)$$

$$B'_0 = B_0 \frac{R_u}{B_u} \quad (11)$$

where: $R_u = 10^{-13}$ m is the unit radius (selected to have the same order of magnitude as $\langle R_e \rangle$), and E_u and B_u are the unit intensities of both fields, having an order of magnitude consistent with the corresponding amplitudes of the E_0 and B_0 of a photon with an energy of 0.511 MeV.

The parametric equations (7)-(9), derived from the known sinusoidal equations of the rectilinear photon [12] (included in the SI together with alternative versions of (7)-(9), see sections 2. and 3.), do not describe the physical contours of the particle, but express a distribution of the electric and magnetic fields intensity around a circle with a radius equal to its quantum radius. This distribution is a periodic function and returns to the original state after 4π . The physical shape of the wave packet of an electron at rest reflects a circle \vec{c}_{loc} , formed from the propagation vector \vec{c} . Incidentally, it has long been pointed out that the electron has probably the form of a ring [27], as indicated by numerous premises reported in [28], including the now forgotten results of experimental research [29]. The shape of a ring as a physically possible type of electric field knot is also consistent with the modern results of quantum-mechanical calculations in [30]. On the other hand, the helix, corresponding to the electron in translational motion, has been mathematically confirmed as the most fundamental particle structure allowed by relativistic physics [31].

The vectors: \vec{R}_c (a leading vector equal to the radius of a circle drawn by the wave front), \vec{E} and \vec{B} , expressed in real physical units and expressing changes in the intensity and direction of both fields can be described as follows:

$$\vec{R}_c = \begin{pmatrix} \langle R_e \rangle \cos \theta \\ \langle R_e \rangle \sin \theta \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$$\vec{E} = \begin{pmatrix} -E_0 \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \cos \theta \\ -E_0 \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \sin \theta \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$\vec{B} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ B_0 \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (14)$$

It should be added that the electron wavenumber resulting from equations (7)-(9) and (12)-(14) and based on the ZBW frequency is a different quantity than the wavenumber of the parent photon. In the case of a rectilinear photon, described in a traditional way, a single oscillation falls on the entire wavelength. Therefore, to describe a photon using systems of equations analogous to (7)-(9) while maintaining a uniform convention, the double wave number should be used (which has been demonstrated in the SI, section 2.).

The switching phases of the electrical component are characterized by a different configuration of field vectors, directed in one of them to the centre of the circle curvature and in the second to the outside. This means that the particle is always directed outwards by vectors representing the same field sign, which is equivalent to the formation of an electric charge (q), because this type of a system with isolated single phase of electrical oscillations must affect a test charge placed within its range [12]. Electric charge is therefore not something like an unidentified substance emitting electric field flux, but simply is this field. Such mechanism of charge generation, based on inverted causality (according to which electric field generates charge) was described in [32] and due to logical reasons it must be at least tacitly assumed in all of the models describing an electron as a form of electromagnetic wave. It can be expressed by the Gaussian law [33], changing the equal sign to identity:

$$q \equiv \varepsilon_0 \oint \vec{E} d\vec{S} \quad (15)$$

where: ε_0 – permittivity of vacuum, \vec{S} – surface.

In the context of the above mechanism of charge formation and the mutual perpendicularity of the directions of an electron \vec{E} and \vec{B} fields oscillation, it must be stated that the electric dipole moment of this particle (eEDM), which has been intensively searched for, is probably located perpendicular to the spin, and not parallel, as is currently assumed [34]. Also, it is related to the asymmetry of the \vec{E} field resulting from the existence of the oscillation phase change point, cf. Fig. 2a. The same conclusion regarding the perpendicular location of the eEDM, although formulated on the basis of a different analysis, describing an electron as a point-like charge and thus not taking into account the asymmetry of its electrical component or its phase change, was presented in [35]. Therefore, the current eEDM measurement procedures should be extended to include research in this alternative direction. This postulate remains valid even if both conceptions of an electron – from [35] and from this article – were to turn out to be wrong. Such an extension is advisable, if only to achieve methodological completeness of the experiment. Since the geometry of fundamental particles is unknown, narrowing the scope of research on the basis of assumptions coming from purely mathematical formalism, not accompanied by an attempt to imagine the physical origin and mechanism of the phenomenon under study, treated as an “intrinsic” property of a particle, should be avoided.

Fig. 2. (a) Location of the electric dipole moment (red arrow) in the quantum structure of an electron relative to the spin (black arrow); (b) mechanism of formation of the spin magnetic moment of an electron due to the change of a phase of the magnetic component oscillation. The drawings were plotted using equations (7)-(9) for the conventional parameters: $\langle R_e \rangle = 1$, $E_0' = 1$ and $B_0' = 1$.

Based on the considered electron model, it is possible to explain the mechanism of generation of the spin magnetic moment with gyromagnetic factor about 2 [36], i.e. twice the analogous factor of the orbital magnetic moment. This mechanism is illustrated in Fig. 2b, which shows the course of the magnetic component of an electron in both phases with the resultant magnetic moment marked with an arrow. As it can be seen, the total shape of the curve drawn by the arrows of the magnetic component vectors in both phases of oscillation corresponds to the Hubius helix, postulated in [37] as the geometric structure of an electron (without interpreting it as a form of electromagnetic wave). Despite the opposite turns of the \vec{B} field vectors in each of these phases (cf. Fig. 1), their individual magnetic moments (μ_+ and μ_-) add up, because they come from magnetic field disturbances of opposite signs – the whole component acts therefore as a dipole. The partial magnetic moment (μ_i), coming from a single phase, can be calculated via a basic equation applied for a current loop (as it is shown in SI, section 4.).

It is worth to notice that the model does not exclude an existence of so far undiscovered electron isomer with an opposite turn of the whole magnetic moment in relation to the spin. Such isomers would not be distinguishable from ordinary electrons in the Stern-Gerlach experiment, but they could have slightly different spintronic properties and unequal probability of annihilation in the interactions with two analogous positron isomers (similarly to enantiomers of some chemical compounds which show different reactivity toward the same reagents due to geometric reasons). A creation of these electron isomers would involve a 270° phase shift in time between electric and magnetic component of the parent photon.

The change of an electron electromagnetic oscillations phase is reflected in the language of quantum-mechanical description as a change of the wave function sign after a 360° rotation, which is still an unsolved mystery of spinors [22]. The wave function, like many other semiotic objects in artificial languages of natural sciences, is a case of an iconic sign, which implies that there must be some kind of analogy between it and the system it represents. Accordingly to that, it can be shown that the particle described by the considered model acts similarly to the spinor in Dirac's theory. Since that model describes an electron as a form of electromagnetic wave, it is logical to use the Riemann-Silberstein (RS) vector, applied as a quantum-mechanical equivalent of the wave function for a photon and defined as $\vec{F} = \vec{E} + i\vec{B}$ [38, 39]. Following the mathematical convention of equations (7)-(9), it has in the case of an electron the form given below:

$$\vec{F}: \begin{cases} x_E = \left(\langle R_e \rangle - E'_0 \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \right) \cos \theta \\ y_E = \left(\langle R_e \rangle - E'_0 \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \right) \sin \theta \\ z_E = iB'_0 \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Fig. 3. Electron as a spinor in the real space: a curve drawn by the end of the Riemann-Silberstein vector in each phase of electromagnetic oscillation: (a) from 0 to 2π (pink) and (b) from 2π to 4π (green); the short black arrows indicate a counter-clockwise direction of changes resulting from the direction of the wave front propagation, while the longer ones indicate the vector itself (red – at the beginning of a phase); (c) the same curve shown together with the diagram of the particle in both phases. The drawings were plotted using equations (7)-(9) and (16) for the conventional parameters: $\langle R_e \rangle = 1$, $E_0' = 1$ and $B_0' = 1$, omitting the imaginary unit present in (16).

A course of the function \vec{F} described by the parametric equations (16) at the full range of θ angles from 0 to 4π is presented in Fig. 3a, b with the \vec{c}_{loc} circle, added for clarity as a set of anchor points of the RS vector (marked by arrows). In Fig. 3c the function \vec{F} is plotted together with the scheme of an electron in both electromagnetic phases to illustrate their mutual relations. As it is easy to see, the RS vector changes its turn after each rotation by 2π , which corresponds with a change of the \vec{F} function sign. Therefore, it is a spinor case. It should be added that the RS vector could be a basis for a future formulation of a universal version of quantum mechanics, including both photons and electrons, especially since, unlike the traditional wave function of an electron, it is a mathematical object with a clear, although indirect physical sense.

The cyclic movement of RS vector with switching of the function \vec{F} sign, illustrated in Fig. 3, is analogous to a movement of an arrow along a Möbius stripe, which would also cause a change in the turn of the arrow after each rotation by 2π . It is consistent with some accurate intuitions regarding an existence of a relationship between an electron and the Möbius stripe, published for example in [19] and expressed by other researchers during discussions at the *models-of-particles@googlegroups.com*, with the slight difference that in those models this stripe was not interpreted exactly as the shape drawn by the RS vector or, at least, it was not stated readable using this term. Thus, it might be understood as a twisted shape of the wave packet drawn directly by the particle \vec{E} vector. A twist unlocking this vector from xy plane is found also in Williamson's model of a toroidal electron [7] but without clear justification for what physical factor could cause it, as well as the double-loop confinement of the parent photon, which was rightly noted in the recent critical review paper [40]. Maybe assuming that the toroidal shape is drawn by the rest electron wave front after performing many orbits, trajectory precession due to non-uniform, sinusoidal distribution of the electric field could be considered as the causative factor. Regardless, the Ockham razor principle orders an initial choice of the simplest, ring shaped wave packet until the Möbius stripe-like or toroidal geometry is experimentally proven fact or logically necessary assumption. Its future verification could be based on experiments carried out in order to investigate the structure of an electron if they start to be feasible. The preliminary part of them

should involve an attempt to create electron-positron pairs from high-energy photons with various polarizations (circular, ellipsoidal and plane) and at systematically changed collision geometries, and then comparing the probability of particle formation to get information about the possible configuration of its electromagnetic field.

The alternating phases of electron oscillations described above give a picture consistent with the concept of so-called internal particle clock, postulated by Louis de Broglie [41] and now experimentally proven [42]. This is also strikingly similar to the results of the research reported in [43], where formation of the spin magnetic moment of an electron was found connected with two different particle's energy states, switching at a frequency consistent with the ZBW and identified with the positive and negative energy solutions of Dirac's equation; their switching was interpreted as the source of $g = 2$ for the spin magnetic moment of an electron. To obtain the correct value of it, including both of these states was necessary [43]. This mechanism works analogously to the scheme demonstrated in Fig. 2b, where two opposite electromagnetic phases of an electron gives together a doubled magnetic moment compared to this after one rotation. Therefore, following the conclusions from [43], a hypothesis can be formulated that attributes the value of the energy gap between the positive and negative solutions of Dirac's equation, equal to $2m_e c^2$, to the energy gap which should emerge between the two electromagnetic phases of an electron due to their different internal quantum geometry.

Even a cursory, qualitative analysis of it indicates that the reason of that energy difference may be some factor related to large asymmetry of the angular oscillation densities of the electrical component when its vectors are directed outwards and inwards of the wave packet curvature, cf. Fig. 4. This unknown factor must be related to internal binding force of an electron far exceeding the Coulomb repulsion force (occurring as a self-interaction due to concentrically arranged \vec{E} vectors with the same sign), which could otherwise lead to a destruction of the particle. Also, this binding factor must act between adjacent cavity points at a short distance. Such an assumption is consistent with the results of nonlinear optic research, during which it was found that for electromagnetic wave bending in strong magnetic field short-range distances are important [14]. The possibility of a mechanism for electron-positron pairs creation and stabilization based on a simple space-time bending is practically excluded due to insufficient mass of these particles [7]. The space-time bending by high local energy density must be rejected as a causative factor as well, because it would lead to spontaneous creation of particles from photons with energy exceeding 0.511 MeV under any conditions, which is not observed.

Fig. 4. Asymmetry of angular energy density carried by the electrical component of an electron in both electromagnetic oscillation phases – the red arrows represent \vec{E} field vectors.

The energy difference between electromagnetic phases of an electron should lead to a difference in its quantum radius: in the “positive” (high energy) phase it must decrease and in the “negative” (low energy) one it must increase, which gives a dynamic image of collapsing and expanding wave packet in the ZBW plane. This image agrees with the well-known law that energy and length of the electromagnetic wave (λ) are related [44]:

$$E = \frac{hc}{\lambda} \quad (17)$$

Thus, in the case of an electron a change of its energy causes a change of its quantum circuit, and so the radius too, and in such a system the radius from the Hestenes’ model is not a constant but an average value. Also, as it can be noticed, the equation (17) requires a positive energy of a rest particle since this energy is correlated with the Compton wavelength which is always positive. Apart from that, the negative energy is forbidden because it would be related to a negative mass (via the dependence $E = m_e c^2$). It deserves an attention in context of the negative solutions of Dirac’s equation, as they are obtained by a normalization procedure, carried out due to the fact that the results of a differential equation are de facto functions, not numbers. Such a normalization is quite arbitrary and so it is possible that in its current version it leads to determining only relative values of the energy, corresponding with the energy gap between the both states of an electron. The absolute values may be all positive and reaching the final result, representing the observable rest-mass energy of the particle, is slightly more complicated.

Applying the above-described model of an electron and the hypothesis of a relationship connecting the switching electromagnetic oscillation phases with the positive and negative solutions of Dirac’s equation, the effect of the energy difference between these states on the quantum geometry of the particle is studied. The expected values of an electron radius in both phases are calculated, based on the value of energy gap between them, equal to $2m_e c^2$, and further analysis is performed assuming that quantum equivalent of the radius from Hestenes’ model [1] is the average value coming from both phases, and the factor stabilizing the particle are some still unrecognized short-range self-interactions. Surprising and mathematically interesting results are obtained.

3. Calculations and discussion

3.1. Quantum radius of an electron in the both electromagnetic phases

Following the dependence (17), the difference in energy between the “positive” and “negative” phase of the particle’s electromagnetic oscillations can be expressed as:

$$\Delta E = hc \left(\frac{1}{\lambda^+} - \frac{1}{\lambda^-} \right) = 2m_e c^2 \quad (18)$$

(where λ^+ and λ^- are the wavelengths corresponding with each phase), which after transformations gives:

$$\frac{\lambda^- - \lambda^+}{\lambda^- \lambda^+} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{2m_e c}{\hbar} = \frac{1}{2\pi(R_e)} \quad (19)$$

Since half of the wavelength ($1/2 \lambda$) in each electromagnetic phase of an electron is equal to the circumference of the circle drawn by the wave front in this phase (i.e. $2\pi R^+$ or $2\pi R^-$), the above equation can be rewritten as:

$$\frac{4\pi R^- - 4\pi R^+}{16\pi^2 R^- R^+} = \frac{1}{2\pi \langle R_e \rangle} \quad (20)$$

Thus, the radius of an electron in both phases is linked by the relation:

$$R^+ = \frac{\langle R_e \rangle R^-}{2R^- + R_e} \quad (21)$$

Based on the above relation it is possible to assess the values of R^+ and R^- . To do this, $\langle R_e \rangle$ being an arithmetic average value of an electron radii in both phases, is assumed. Such a simplification, omitting an impact of time, is forced by the fact that the individual phase durations are unknown; it is also justified by the extremely high value of the ZBW frequency, giving time of each phase tending to 0. Inserting the above R^+ value into this average, we get an equation with one factor unknown:

$$\langle R_e \rangle = \frac{R^- + R^+}{2} = \frac{R^- + \frac{\langle R_e \rangle R^-}{2R^- + \langle R_e \rangle}}{2} \quad (22)$$

The transformations of the above expression lead to the below quadratic equation:

$$(R^-)^2 - \langle R_e \rangle R^- - \langle R_e \rangle^2 = 0 \quad (23)$$

The solution of this equation is following:

$$R^- = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \langle R_e \rangle = \varphi \langle R_e \rangle \quad (24)$$

where φ is the golden number, equal to approximately 1.618 (the second solution should of course be omitted, because the radius of a circle cannot be less than zero). This number, known since ancient times [45], is associated with the golden ratio, very common in nature [46], what is reflected in physical description of such objects and phenomena as, for example, systems of coupled mechanical oscillators of equal masses [47], neutrino mixing [48], the behaviour of photons near black holes [49], and even electromagnetism [50] or quantum phenomena related to ferromagnetism [51]. It appears in the solutions of soliton equations, as well [52], and is used by so-called q-calculus, based on the Fibonacci oscillators [53]. What is particularly interesting, φ is present also in the quantum-mechanical uncertainty principle formulated for photons [39], which after simple mathematical transformation (shown in the SI, sections 5. and 6.) can be written as:

$$\Delta P \Delta R \geq \hbar \left(\varphi + \frac{1}{2} \right) \quad (25)$$

After inserting the determined R^- value into equation (21), the quantum radius of an electron in the second phase is obtained:

$$R^+ = \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \langle R_e \rangle \quad (26)$$

As it can be seen, $R^- = \varphi^3 R^+$, thus the golden number is a factor that scales the quantum radius of an electron in both electromagnetic phases.

3.2. Energy dependences

On the basis of the obtained R^+ and R^- values it is possible to calculate further parameters characterizing both states of an electron, i.e. circumference of the model circle, duration of the phase, angular velocity of the wave front propagation, the magnetic moment and energy (the table with these values is presented in the SI, section 7.). As for the energy calculated from R^+ and R^- , the results are as follows:

$$E_\lambda^+ = m_e c^2 (\varphi + 1) \quad (27)$$

$$E_\lambda^- = m_e c^2 (\varphi - 1) \quad (28)$$

It is easy to notice that the energy of an electron in both phases is positive, unlike in the solutions of Dirac's equation for an electron at rest. It is also not an exact analogue of those results in terms of physical sense, nor an equivalent of total energy, but only electromagnetic energy resulting from the wavelength (so it is marked with a subscript λ). Incidentally, it is worth noting that subtracting from both values obtained the same factor, equal to $m_e c^2 \varphi$, leads to results identical to the solutions of the Dirac's equation. Thus, some further relations between these solutions and the values given by (27) and (28) may exist (and they will be later considered).

As it is shown below, the energy value of the rest electron that results from its observed mass ($E = m_e c^2$), is slightly lower than the average value calculated from (27) and (28):

$$\frac{m_e c^2 (\varphi + 1) + m_e c^2 (\varphi - 1)}{2} = \frac{2 m_e c^2 \varphi}{2} = m_e c^2 \varphi \quad (29)$$

However, this discrepancy is nothing strange, because in an oscillating system some kind of potential energy may emerge, being in this case the factor stabilizing an electron and fixing its circular shape after the transformation from a free, rectilinear photon. It is suggested by the fact that this energy must have negative value to eliminate the above excess (and, as it is known, negative potential energy is an indicator of a system durability). Thus, the energy stored in the particle's rest mass is its total energy, being a sum of the energy resulting from the wavelength and the internal potential energy ($\langle E_p \rangle$), which can be determined as follow:

$$\langle E_p \rangle = -(m_e c^2 \varphi - m_e c^2) = -m_e c^2 (\varphi - 1) \quad (30)$$

It is the average (resultant) potential energy from both phases. If it was sure that the dependence of this energy on the quantum radius of the particle is described by an equation of the general form $E_p(R) = aR^n$, it would be possible to determine precisely the individual shares coming from each of them applying the well-known Clausius virial theorem. However, the exact form of this dependence is unknown, therefore such calculations are done as a rough assessment. Also, a second, complementary method of the potential energy shares assessment,

based directly on the analysis of the proportions of the particle's quantum radius in each phase to $\langle R_e \rangle$, is applied to compare the results and obtain more comprehensive view.

For the calculations based on the virial theorem, it is assumed by analogy to the spin, being an internal electron angular momentum, that the wave front of the particle has also an equivalent of kinetic energy, given by $1/2 m_e c^2$. As a result, $n = -\varphi$ is obtained, giving $E_p(R) = aR^{-\varphi}$. Applying the dependence: $(E_{\lambda^+} + E_{\lambda^-} + E_p^+ + E_p^-)/2 = m_e c^2$, the a coefficient is determined as: $a = [(-2(\varphi)^{\varphi-1})\langle R_e \rangle^{\varphi}]/(1+(1/\varphi^3)^{-\varphi})m_e c^2$. The final calculations leads to the following potential energy values and masses for each phase: $E_p^+ \cong -1.127 m_e c^2$, $m_e^+ \cong 1.491 m_e$, $E_p^- \cong -0.109 m_e c^2$, and $m_e^- \cong 0.509 m_e$. The occurrence of two different masses in this system is consistent with the fact that the fundamental particles' mass shows an inverse correlation with their size [54], so, in this case, with the R^+ and R^- . Despite that, the average mass of an electron agrees with the observed value and remains constant beyond the time scale of the fermionic quantum ZBW cycle (i.e. rotation in the range of 0-720°). And due to the fact that there are only two electromagnetic phases (and so, two discrete masses, not a continuum), they can be considered as something like two quantum (or rather “sub-quantum”) states. Furthermore, it should be noted that for a radius equal to $\langle R_e \rangle$ the potential energy would be $E_p(\langle R_e \rangle) \cong -0.237 m_e c^2$ which gives an electron mass: $m_e(\langle R_e \rangle) \cong 0.763 m_e$. It shows that accordingly to the proposed model a constant radius equal to $\langle R_e \rangle$ is forbidden by the energy conservation law which requires a resultant value of the energy stored in the form of particle's mass to be equal to the energy of the parent photon. In a system with negative potential energy binding the wave packet this principle can be satisfied if and only if oscillations occur, giving the appropriate value of the rest mass energy as the average from the two states. Of course, the oscillations are driven also by the electromagnetic phase change itself, and by the shift between the sinusoidal changing \vec{E} and \vec{B} , which makes these components acting similarly to a pair of coupled oscillators.

The calculations based directly on the proportions of the particle's quantum radius in each phase to $\langle R_e \rangle$ could be possible to perform in several variants, but only one of them satisfies the criteria of the correct electron's average mass together with the potential energy of the mean value equal to $-(\varphi-1)m_e c^2$, different in each individual phase, and always negative, as it is a condition of the particle's stability (E_p reaches zero for a rectilinear photon, which can be considered as it would propagate along a circle with infinitesimally large radius). This variant of calculations is given by the below equation:

$$E_p^i = \frac{\langle E_p \rangle + \left(1 - \frac{\langle R_e \rangle}{R^i}\right) m_e c^2}{2} \quad (31)$$

where i index marks the conventional sign “+” or “-”.

The results are following:

$$E_p^+ = -m_e c^2 \left(\varphi - \frac{1}{2}\right) = -\left(1 + \frac{1}{2\varphi^3}\right) m_e c^2 \cong -1.118 m_e c^2 \quad (32)$$

$$E_p^- = -m_e c^2 \left(\varphi - \frac{3}{2}\right) = -\left(\frac{1}{2\varphi^3}\right) m_e c^2 \cong -0.118 m_e c^2 \quad (33)$$

The masses of an electron in both phases are, appropriate, $1.5 m_e$ (in the “positive” phase) and $0.5 m_e$ (in the “negative” one) so, they are comparable with those obtained from the virial theorem ($1.491 m_e$ and $0.509 m_e$ appropriately). Thus, they can be considered as a reasonable second approximation. At the present stage it is not possible to decide which of these approximations is more accurate but the second is mathematically more elegant.

3.3. Internal half-oscillator

The values of an electron’s internal potential energy, given by (32) and (33), can be easily described in terms of traditional quantum mechanics, applying a slightly modified formula for the eigenvalues of a quantum harmonic oscillator:

$$E_p^i = -\frac{1}{2} \hbar \langle \omega \rangle \left(n' + \frac{1}{2\varphi^3} \right) \quad (34)$$

where only two states are possible (the state $n' = 0$, being the lower energy phase, i.e. the “negative” one with the value “-“ of the i index, and $n' = 1$, being the higher energy phase, i.e. the “positive” one, indexed as “+”); $\langle \omega \rangle$ represents average ZBW (identical with the value given in [1]):

$$\langle \omega \rangle = \frac{c}{\langle R_e \rangle} = \frac{2m_e c^2}{\hbar} \quad (35)$$

The symbol n' in (34) is introduced to avoid a confusion of the internal half-oscillator states of a rest electron with the states of an oscillator from the higher level of quantum mechanics (as they are usually marked by n).

Similarly, the particle’s quantum radius (R^i), the electromagnetic energy assigned to a wavelength resulting from it (E_λ^i) and the energy in a form of the rest mass of each phase (E_m^i) are expressed by the formulas:

$$R^i = \frac{1}{2n' + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2\varphi^3}} \langle R_e \rangle \quad (36)$$

$$E_\lambda^i = \frac{1}{2} \hbar \langle \omega \rangle \left(2n' + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2\varphi^3} \right) \quad (37)$$

$$E_m^i = \frac{1}{2} \hbar \langle \omega \rangle \left(n' + \frac{1}{2} \right) \quad (38)$$

Analogous half-oscillator equations for the virial approximation are presented in the SI, section 8.

It should be emphasized that the both states of the above described half-oscillator belong to the ground state of an electron and break its time-translation symmetry. Therefore, such a particle is a case of time crystal [55, 56, 57]. It must be added, that the connection between time crystals and electron oscillations due to ZBW was noticed for the first time in the theoretical study [58], based solely on energy minimization and interpreting the mechanism of these oscillations as caused only by mass.

3.4. Normalization of Dirac's equation solutions for the rest electron

On the basis of the above presented results it is possible to propose a new version of the normalization of the solutions of Dirac's equation for the rest electron to solve so-called negative-energy problem without involving additional antiparticle which moves backward in time, as it was proposed by Richard Feynman [59]. Such a phenomenon as moving any object backward in time is not empirically proven and, to make matters worse, assuming it leads to many logical inconsistencies. For example, the positive-time particle could exist infinitesimally long while its antiparticle moving backward in time could exist only until it reach the moment of its creation; after that it must disappear which would destroy an equilibrium in the quantum system and its completeness. This is due to the fact that moving backward in time is a relative process, theoretically possible if and only if there exist a reference frame in which an object A moves in time at the direction according to the time arrow and an object B at the direction opposite. In such a situation B must reach some point t_0 , being the beginning of its existence. If the direction of the time axis is changed to the opposite, A must reach its t_0 . It is easy to conclude that if the condition of reaching t_0 by any of two objects moving in the opposite time directions is satisfied in one reference frame, it must be satisfied in the all possible ones. And, on the other hand, if the direction opposite to the time axis is assigned to an antiparticle from the beginning of its existence, it must be annihilated at once; if this antiparticle is travelling backward in time not from the beginning, it had to change the direction of its travel from the previous forward. In such a case it would be hardly to justify it, because the physical factor which could force that change is unknown.

Moreover, even the assumption of a parallel presence of two particles instead of one in the rest system described by Dirac's equation causes a serious problem, this time concerning the energy conservation law: the sum of the amounts coming from these particles would be 0 ($m_e c^2 + (-m_e c^2)$) although it is known that they both must have positive masses, carrying together the sum of energy of their parent photons. Also, explaining the negative energy as coming from the opposite sign of an antiparticle charge would be not justified, because there exist many particles experimentally confirmed as having opposite charges and always positive rest mass energy. As electrons and positrons both are fermions and have the same mass, any solution of Dirac's equation obtained for one of them is valid also in the case of the second one by analogy and there is no good reason to link the negative energy solutions with positrons and the positive ones with electrons.

Last but not least, the two-particles interpretation causes inconsistency of Dirac's equation with the Schrödinger's one, which should not occur, due to the fact that the rest electron is nonrelativistic particle, so in this boundary case the solutions of these equations should be compatible, especially in the aspect of the resulting particles number. Therefore, probably none of the four individual Dirac's equation solutions represents an independent quantum state, correlated with an observable, but a component of such a state. And so, this equation not only predicts spin as an inherent electron's property, resulting from the demand for relativistic invariance, but reveals also a fingerprint of a deeper, "sub-quantum" level of this particle's physics in the Hilbert space, corresponding with the two switching electromagnetic phases in the real space. Due to their different energy and quantum geometry,

they must appear as if they were two various particles and the observable electron is something like their “superposition” or averaged form.

In the proposed modified mathematical procedure, the traditional normalization is the first stage of the calculations; its aim is to determine the value of energy gap between the rest electron’s states. After that, an additional boundary condition is introduced, requiring the positive energy of an electron to obtain consistency of the solutions with the equation (17) which excludes negative energy of a free particle at rest as it would be correlated with a negative value of its Compton wavelength (and thus the quantum radius). Based on it, the quantum radius of an electron in both phases is calculated applying equations (18)-(25) and the further analysis is performed to determine the difference between the observed rest mass of an electron and its electromagnetic energy, i.e. the parameter $m_e c^2 \phi$. Then, this parameter is identified as a constant which should be added to the solutions of Dirac’s equation to obtain the two different but positive values of energy described by (27) and (28). And although they have a certain physical sense (two asymmetric ZBW states of the electromagnetic energy of an electron), it is still not the final result, since they do not represent complete information about the system: the potential energy binding the particle is not included. Adding the determined $m_e c^2 \phi$ constant to the Dirac’s equation solutions leads to the quantum harmonic half-oscillator. As a result, the two values of the rest mass energy of an electron are obtained from (38), however it is not the last operation as well. It should be noticed that they both amount to the same ground quantum state of the particle (and so to its observable mass, too), therefore they should not be separated (only at a deeper, “sub-quantum” level of internal electron physics they are independent states). Thus, the solution is only one: it is the mean of these two values, representing the expected rest mass energy of an electron, which results from the whole fermionic ZBW cycle (0-720°), returning the particle to its initial state:

$$\langle E_m \rangle = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^1 \frac{1}{2} \hbar \langle \omega \rangle (n + \frac{1}{2})}{2} \quad (39)$$

More precisely, there are two solutions: for an electron with spin up and down, but they are not distinguishable in the rest frame without an external magnetic field (due to the same value of their energy). This approach not only correlates well with the fermionic properties of an electron, but also provides consistency between the Dirac’s and Schrödinger’s equations.

The above described procedure of normalization of Dirac’s equation solutions can be applied also if the considered physical model of an electron as a form of electromagnetic wave is seem to be unrealistic (or not proven enough at the present stage of the experimental techniques development), because even in such a case it still represents a kind of quantum equivalent of this particle’s geometry. Therefore, it works similarly to the well-known orthodox concept of a spin which is defined as an analogue of the classical angular momentum, however occurring without any real, physical movement.

3.5. Hypothesis about a physical nature of the internal electron bond

Here it is necessary to comment on the term $1/(2\phi^3)$ in (34) because it is another mathematical surprise: this term is equal to the value of strong interaction coupling constant,

$\alpha_s = 0.118$ [60]. Its explicit presence in the results obtained on the potential energy of an electron's internal binding suggests that the nature of this energy may be related to that interaction, previously known as the binding force of nucleons and quarks inside complex particles [61]. It has a short range, $\sim 10^{-15}$ m, thus it works at the Fermi scale, corresponding with so-called classical radius of an electron. It is not excluded that this parameter characterizes in some way (at this stage yet unknown) the cavity where the binding force, based on the strong interaction, acts. Although an electron is indivisible, a gluon carrying this interaction can be emitted inside the cavity or, interpreting the mechanism of this interaction in a slightly different way, it can result directly from the angular density of electromagnetic oscillations, since it is independent of the Coulomb interactions. Incidentally, the electromagnetic nature of the strong interaction has long been considered in the literature [62], because at sufficiently high energies, all constants known from the Standard Model are unified [63]. In this context, it is also worth noting that nucleons and quarks are physical objects from different levels of matter organization, so following this, the strong force may be a more universal factor, stabilizing all indivisible particles as well, as a kind of their internal self-interaction, even if they do not interact by this force with other species. Since it is about 100 times stronger than the Coulomb one, it effectively blocks particle's destruction.

3.6. Anomalous magnetic moment of an electron

At the end of the analysis, it can be shown one more intriguing mathematical fact revealed by the analysis of the quantum geometry of an electron, concerning this time its anomalous magnetic moment (a_e).

Experimentally determined value of this parameter ($(a_e)_{EXP}$) [64] is equal to a half of the difference between so-called Lande g-factor (g_e) of this particle and its gyromagnetic factor predicted by the Dirac's theory ($g = 2$):

$$(a_e)_{EXP} = \left(\frac{g_e - 2}{2} \right)_{EXP} = 0.00115965218046 \mp 1.8 \times 10^{-13} \quad (40)$$

As it is believed, the origin of that difference are electromagnetic interactions of an electron with virtual particles. Therefore, theoretical value of a_e is calculated by means of the quantum electrodynamic (QED) tools; the full computing procedure consists of several stages (presented in SI, section 9.) and is still developed in some aspects [65]. The discrepancy between the calculated ($(a_e)_{QED}$) value and the experimental result amounts to 9.1×10^{-13} [66].

Applying the half-oscillator formalism, this parameter can be determined (in a manner shown in SI, section 10.) as:

$$a_e = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\frac{1}{2} + \alpha_s} + \frac{1}{\frac{5}{2} + \alpha_s} \right) - 1 \quad (41)$$

When idealized α_s , derived directly from the golden number (i.e. $\alpha_s = 0.118033988749$), is assumed, we obtain from (41) $a_e = 0$ and thus the gyromagnetic factor of an electron equals to 2, exactly like in the Dirac's theory. Taking $\alpha_s = 0.1179$, which is the current world mean value (0.1179 ± 0.0009 [67]), results in nonzero but too small a_e (0.000185220644), however

$\alpha_s = 0.117195948$ (consistent, as well, with the currently reported values of this constant) provides a_e identical with the experimental one. Such a correction does not change the particle's mass, dependent only on the quantum number n' , see equation (38). So, the proposed model of an electron could enable describing the anomalous magnetic moment of this particle as its inherent feature, related to the electromagnetic phase asymmetry, without a need of considering interactions with virtual particles.

On the other hand, calculations giving the dependence (41) are based on the parameters taken directly from Dirac's theory, thus obtaining a_e equal to 0 is expected. This theory does not describe any processes occurring inside of a particle, therefore, a future study including additional details, especially a possible concurrence between the anti-binding (coulombic) and the binding (strong) self-interactions of an electron, should be performed and other forces which may influence the α_s , making it slightly lower than the model value, should be researched. A preliminary work on this, including an analysis of purely mathematical relationships between a_e , α_s , α and the golden number, yields an astonishing result. It enables to find independently another simple and regular formula involving α_s and calculating a_e with amazing accuracy. The discovered dependence, presented earlier in [68] and complementary to other mathematical relations between the golden number, the fine-structure constant and the anomalous magnetic moment of an electron [69, 70], is following:

$$a_e = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{360-1}{\varphi^2} + \alpha_s\right)2\pi} \quad (42)$$

Despite its simplicity, the equation (42) shows very high predictive efficiency: substituting into it $\alpha_s = 0.11789$ (slightly more accurate than the world mean value, 0.1179 ± 0.0009) leads to $a_e = 0.001159652188$ (with an error at the level of 10^{-12} , comparable with the a_e value computed applying quantum electrodynamic tools). Even substituting α_s value estimated roughly as 0.118 still enables calculating a_e matched with the experimental and theoretical results up to the eighth decimal place; thus, the formula (42) is not only accurate but error-resistant as well. The term $(360-1)/\varphi^2$, equal to 137.125798, so quite close to $1/\alpha$, may represent something like an "effective" value of it in the internal system of an electron, because after inserting $1/\alpha$ instead of $(360-1)/\varphi^2$ in (42) and removing α_s the formula $\alpha/2\pi$, being the first term applied in the traditional a_e computing, is obtained. The sum of the "effective" $1/\alpha$ and α_s in the denominator of the fraction in (42) seems to describe some kind of an equilibrium between the coulombic and the strong self-interactions inside of an electron, determining the value of a_e .

Although at the current stage of the research a clear relation between (41) and (42) is difficult to find, the fact that a_e can be easily and yet very accurately calculated when α_s is taken into account, is a premise in favour of the hypothesis of the internal strong self-interaction as the factor stabilizing an electron and influencing a_e , because such perfect result suggests that it may be not only a mathematical curio but a possible natural law which deserves further investigation. If confirmed in the future, the equation (42) can be applied for determining the strong interaction coupling constant on the basis of the electron Lande g-factor measurements. It would make the technical procedures significantly easier and cheaper

and also improve the accuracy of experimental α_s values by several orders of magnitude comparing to the contemporary results (to obtain a_e value ideally matched with the experimental one, $\alpha_s = 0.117890958$ should be assumed instead of 0.1179 ± 0.0009). If the hypothesis is not confirmed, the dependence (42) can still be useful as a convenient practical tool, because it is elegant and easy to remember.

3. Conclusions

The performed meta-analysis, based on the ZBW interpretation of quantum mechanics, leads to a new variant of a model of an electron being nonlinear form of electromagnetic wave. This is a synthesis of the previous concepts, corrected and enriched with further aspects, especially the description of energetic asymmetry of the electromagnetic oscillations phases arising from the fermionic properties of the particle. It has to be emphasized that it has not been decided whether the considered model of an electron as a form of photon is physically correct (as a literal representation of reality), because at the current stage of experimental techniques development it cannot be verified; it can be also a somewhat simplistic image. Nevertheless, it is a well-founded hypothesis, with a high probability of truth, due to the fact that it is based on numerous premises and a rich set of data from various branches of natural sciences. Above all, however, it is a good model equivalent of the “substance” of an electron, because since both particles have so many common features and the concept fits perfectly with the image of an electron encoded in quantum mechanics, its use in further research may have a high predictive power, helping to discover and explain further phenomena related to this particle.

Just like the previous models of an electron, the elements of which have been adopted, the proposed variant explains many incomprehensible to this day quantum-mechanical properties of this particle. At the same time, it removes the problem of electrical component internal twist, present in the most advanced but probably too complicated models with an electron’s shape based on a torus or a Möbius stripe; here the geometry of an electron is simpler and the Möbius-like topology emerges on a more abstract level, as a form of a function representing the changes of the RS vector. An attempt to describe the studied particle using this vector as an analogue of the wave function led to obtaining equations acting as a spinor. This also shows the possible relationships between the quantum and electromagnetic phases of an electron wave packet and explain the differences between fermions and bosons, especially the reason of a change of an electron wave function sign after a 360° rotation. The performed analysis may be a starting point for a universal quantum mechanics development, encompassing electrons and photons, which would be a more elegant theory than the current one. In addition, replacing the traditional wave function of an electron with the RS vector would have one more advantage that it is a mathematical object with a legible physical sense.

The calculation part of the article reveals interesting mathematical relationships between a photon and an electron created from it. The consequences which may result from the assumption of the energy asymmetry of the two described electromagnetic phases of an electron and the differences of the particle’s quantum radius in each of them are discussed. It

is shown that a free rest electron at the ground state can act as a half-oscillator in which various types of energy coexist; it is also a dynamic object with no fixed radius. The obtained values of the negative internal potential energy, related in an interesting way to the strong force coupling constant, may indicate that this force is not only a binding factor for nucleons and quarks, but also for indivisible particles, working at a short distance inside of their cavity. Including this constant to the calculation of the anomalous magnetic moment of an electron leads to obtaining the value of this parameter in an easy way with accuracy at the level of contemporary quantum electrodynamics computing. The half-oscillator approach enables a modification of the Dirac's equation normalization procedure to solve the negative-energy problem, up to now explained in terms of an antiparticle correlated with the electron and moving backward in time.

The analysis results in certain postulates for experiments and theoretical investigations.

Firstly, the current eEDM measurement procedure should be extended including a direction perpendicular to the spin. The premise for this is not only the quantum-mechanical picture of the geometry of an electron, but even the nature of electromagnetic field with both components mutually perpendicular in most physical systems, which indicates that also the magnetic moment and the electric dipole moment of fundamental particles may show an analogous perpendicularity. And even if it were to turn out that for some reason this is not the case, it would be right to check it.

Secondly, it would be worth conducting research involving the creation of electron-positron pairs from high-energy photons with different polarizations, handedness and propagation geometry, if it starts to be technically feasible, in order to analyse the results in terms of possible differences in the probability of the particles formation. This could be a preliminary stage of pioneering experimental study on an electron's structure and on the mechanism of light-matter phase transition.

Thirdly, it is worth investigating the potential influence of chirality and helicity of an electron on its spintronic properties, because since the wave front of an electron moves along the helix, the direction of its turn in relation to the direction of the magnetic moment in a given system with an external magnetic field can affect the energy of the particle and thus the preferred spin arrangement.

In a broader methodological context, the analysis shows the limitations of traditional quantum mechanics. The results can set new direction for research in this field, aimed at creating and testing electron models which take into account the dynamics of its internal transformations, although so far this way of thinking has struggled to make its way in the mainstream science, due to the need of using unconventional methodology, exploring a broad, interdisciplinary context, and also setting bold hypotheses. This is a difficult way, full of risk. However following it, we can notice that not only the negative energy problem with Dirac's equation solutions but also other unsolved problems of the contemporary physics may be in fact not problems but a fingerprint of some hidden laws of nature to be discovered.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Data availability

All data used as material for the meta-analysis are available in the literature cited or come directly from the calculations provided in the article and SI.

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